

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Learning music similarity using audio and textual input

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Abstract

The incredibly large amount of music that is available online nowadays has created a need for powerful retrieval and recommendation algorithms. Most music streaming services make use of matrix-factorisation collaborative filtering algorithms. While these systems are effective, they have a number of limitations: the fact that they are *content-agnostic* leads to the *cold-start problem* (the model is unable to recommend new and unpopular songs), and the user cannot search for specific elements that can only be extracted from a song's audio. The aim of this thesis was to develop a query-by-example system that can focus on specific aspects of a query song, such as 'instrumentation', 'mood', 'era' or 'genre', thus increasing user control. To this end, we compared two methods: (1) a feature-weighting method, that places higher weight on parts of song embeddings that are relevant to the aspect we want to focus on (2) a metric learning approach that encodes information about different aspects of a song in separate parts of its embedding. We applied the feature-weighting method to both content-based and collaborative filtering-based embeddings such as *Weighted Matrix Factorisation* (WMF) item factors, whereas we only the disentangled metric learning approach for content-based embeddings. The methods were evaluated quantitatively by inspecting tag co-occurrence between query- and retrieved songs, and qualitatively by inspecting retrieval examples and t-SNE visualisations of the song embeddings. It was found that WMF naturally groups together songs with shared semantic tags, and cannot be outperformed by the content-based disentangled metric learning method. However, the content-based method has the advantage of not suffering from the *cold-start problem*. Furthermore, the feature-weighting method was found to improve performance for both content-based tagging embeddings and WMF. Overall, we provide valuable insight into the differences between CF-based and content-based retrieval systems, and provide recommendations on how they can be combined effectively.

Keywords: Music Recommendation, Collaborative filtering, Content-based, Deep learning, Convolutional Neural Networks

Chapter 1

Introduction

Since the advent of online music streaming services like *Spotify*, *Google Music* and *SoundCloud*, music is more easily available and in greater quantities than ever before. However, the abundance means that for most users the majority of songs remain undiscovered. It often proves challenging to find songs that are similar to and as enjoyable as one's favourites. Most music streaming services use algorithms for recommending tracks based on a user's listening behaviour with a technique called collaborative filtering. Collaborative filtering essentially compares listening behaviour (play counts) among users to find patterns. This method might provide a satisfactory experience for many users, but it suffers from the so called cold-start problem, which describes the tendency of these methods to recommend the most popular tracks, overlooking newer and less popular material .

Content-based music recommendation methods aim to find patterns in music itself, eliminating the need for usage data and alleviating the cold-start problem. Automatically learning to extract information from music is the main focus of the field of *music information retrieval* (MIR). Previously, MIR methods used handcrafted features like chroma, a condensed description the tonal content of a musical audio signal, and MFCCs, a representation derived from a signal's Fourier Spectrum, which was originally developed for speech recognition. But increasingly, researchers use Deep learning algorithms (see section 3.3), to automatically learn features from

music. In its rawest form, digital music consists of a sequence of thousands of floating point numbers, which is difficult to interpret and requires a lot of memory. Therefore, audio signals are often converted to an image-like feature representation, which are easier to interpret than raw audio and allows computer vision techniques to be applied. This is favourable, as computer vision is currently one of the most successful fields of artificial intelligence, and has advanced significantly by virtue of deep learning.

Learning to process music like humans do, is a difficult task; there is a specific research field dedicated to the way humans perceive and judge music, called Music Perception and Cognition. There are many characteristics in music that influence user preference, like mood, genre, key or instrumentation, a highly powerful model is required to accurately learn music similarity.

1.1 Motivation

As a music lover with a very broad taste, Spotify is one of the greatest advantages of having access to mobile internet in all of Europe. Streaming music in an easy-to-use app allows me to listen to everything I want, whenever I want, without having to deal with lack of storage on my phone, or having to decide if I like a song enough to buy it. Since a couple of years, Spotify offers personalised playlists such as “Discover Weekly” and “Release Radar”, helping users to discover new music in the abundance that is available. My personal experience is that sometimes Spotify gets it right and I find a lot of songs I like, and other times it’s a complete miss. The main reason for that (I think) is that Spotify bases recommendations on the music I have recently listened to and when I listen to a lot of different styles in a week, it gets confused. Furthermore, I miss a sense of control when I am specifically digging for a certain type of music. Very often, I wish to find more music comparable to a particular song, and I know exactly which elements of the song I like most. In this situation, the “song radio” features of Spotify (or YouTube, or SoundCloud) rarely give me the results I’m looking for. The feature I’m missing is being able to indicate

a seed/query song, while giving the algorithm instructions of what (in the form of textual description, or selection of a specific section/instrument in the song) to focus on.

1.2 Objectives

- Developing a query-by-example music retrieval system, that can focus on different aspects of songs
- Discovering the differences between collaborative filtering-based systems and content-based systems

1.3 Structure of the Report

The report is structured as follows: (2) Related Work - discussion of previous work and relevant literature and formulation of research questions (3) Methods - explanation of technical concepts and theoretical frameworks (4) Experiments & Results - experiments to compare proposed methods (5) Discussion - examination of the empirical findings (6) Conclusions & Future work - summary of the thesis and ideas for future work

Chapter 2

Related Work

2.1 Music similarity

Assessment of similarity is a fundamental human capability which is important for categorization processes [36]. In the context of MIR it is a fundamental principle to retrieve music. Due to the availability of large amounts of digitized musical data there is a need to develop methods that enable users to search within large collections of music. Thus, the notion of music similarity is a central concept in realizing the access to musical collections: for a given query of the user, similar pieces within the collection should be determined. In general, similarity is defined in terms of broad categories such as genre, under the assumption that songs belonging to the same category are more similar to each other than to songs belonging to other categories. However, MIR often faces the challenge of a lack of domain knowledge on finer grained music similarity going beyond broad categories such as genres, and therefore a lack of human similarity data that computational algorithms can be tested on.

Novello et al. [24] discuss the lack of music similarity assessment algorithms linked to human perception. In an attempt to answer several open questions (do subjects have a common perception of music similarity? What are the principal perceptual features used by subjects in rating similarity? Which features are most relevant? Is there a

significant influence of musical experience?) they propose an empirical method for assessing human perception of similarity. After collecting 2 audio excerpts for each of 9 different genres (one fast and one slow song per genre), a dataset was formed by combining different song excerpts into triads/triplets. Subjects were asked to listen to a set of three song-excerpts (triads) and choose for each comparison the most similar and most dissimilar of the three possible pairs. Statistical tests were performed to assess inter- and intra-subject consistency. The data show general agreement across subjects. Finally, multi-dimensional scaling (MDS) was used to represent subjects' rankings in a multidimensional metrical space. Distances in the metrical space seem to confirm the presumption that genre is an important dimension in human similarity judgement (more so than tempo).

However, this is directly contradicted in two works by Flexer et al. (Flexer et al. [8], Flexer et al. [7]). They argue that limited inter-rater agreement in modelling music similarity is a fundamental problem in obtaining ground-truth information. They perform user surveys and show that users do not generally agree about which pieces of music are the most similar. Consequently, they conclude that since it is not meaningful to have computational models that go beyond the level of human agreement, the levels of inter-rater agreement present a natural upper bound for any algorithmic approach.

Computational algorithms for predicting music similarity generally fall into two categories: (1) content-based methods, which try to extract discriminative features from song audio to be compared using similarity/distance metrics such as cosine similarity (2) collaborative-filtering (CF) based methods, which only take into account user data collected from media streaming services to find patterns, and do not use any audio-based information (they are "content-agnostic"). Additionally, some algorithms exist, that combine elements from both methodologies. In the following sections, the most relevant works belonging to the two categories will be discussed.

2.2 Content-based approaches

In general, content-based methods work by condensing low-level acoustic features into a compact vector representation, which facilitates the calculation of vector-based similarity/distance metrics.

Vignoli et al. [35] propose a similarity model that takes into consideration different facets of music (timbre, tempo, genre, mood, and year). Frame-wise timbre features are compared between songs using a Monte Carlo approach: feature vectors for all songs in the database are first clustered using a Self Organizing Map (SOM), then all feature vectors for a song are assigned to cluster centroids and the representation is normalised to represent a probability distribution. Timbre similarity is then calculated as the KL divergence between distributions. Genre, mood, year, and tempo dissimilarities are computed by a using distance function for clustering symbolic objects. The overall similarity is given by the weighted sum of the different similarity components, where the weights are adjustable. In this way, a user has the possibility to change the similarity function that is applied to the music collection. This work is unique in the sense that it directly models different facets of similarity, which is probably necessary for accurately modelling human similarity assessment. Most other works only use timbre features to predict similarity.

For example, West et al. [38] extract temporal and MFCC features from 4510 tracks from the Magnatune collection and train different genre classification models. The tested classifier algorithms are linear discriminant analysis (LDA) and a classification and regression tree (CART). The logit vectors predicted by the genre classification models are used as "profiles" describing songs. The similarity between songs is defined as the euclidean distance between their profile vectors. The performance is evaluated by counting genre, album and artist co-occurrence of retrieved similar songs.

Ellis et al. [6] propose using "beat-synchronous representations for music similarity": instead of trying to condense the information of a song into a single representation, this approach first calculates the beat grid of a song and condenses features/info

per beat. The idea is that this should preserve more of the temporal information. After preprocessing songs like this, the similarity between a pair is calculated by calculating the cross-correlation between beat-synchronous feature representation sequences. Results are evaluated using a user survey. Unfortunately, the baselines, which do condense the song into a single vector, outperform this approach.

Lu et al. [20] train a neural network with a CNN feature extractor and a fully connected "metric net" to learn the relative similarity information in the MagnaTagATune (MTT) dataset. This similarity data consists of triplets of songs, where for each triplet, the least similar among the three is indicated. The neural network, known as a triplet network, predicts a distance metric between pairs of songs. The model is then optimized to predict a larger distance for the dissimilar songs in the ground truth triplets.

Lee et al. [18] use metric learning using triplet loss to learn similarity based on semantic tags. They assume that songs that share the same semantic tag (e.g. 'guitar') are similar in some way. By categorising the used semantic tags into four categories (genre, instrumentation, tempo, mood), the way in which the songs are similar is narrowed down. They apply CNN feature extractor to song spectrograms and use the method proposed by Veit et al. [34] to encode information about the different similarity dimensions (genre, instrumentation, tempo, mood) into separate parts of the song representation.

2.3 Collaborative Filtering approaches

Instead of trying to find similarities by feature representations extracted from song audio, collaborative filtering (CF) approaches leverage user-interaction data to find patterns. User-interaction data is generally categorized into *explicit feedback* and *implicit feedback*. Explicit feedback requires a user to consciously quantify their appreciation of an item, by submitting as a rating or a review, whereas implicit feedback, such as the number of times a user has listened to a song, only requires passive interaction. Implicit feedback has the advantage that it is very easy to

collect in large quantities. Implicit feedback data, such as song play counts, can be represented as large item-user matrices $R \in \mathbb{R}^{i \times u}$ with i the number of songs/items and u the number of users. If a user has listened to an item, the cell corresponding to that user and item is nonzero. As most users only listen to a relatively small subset of the total number of songs available in a streaming service's database for example, most cells of the item-user matrix are zero. The goal of a collaborative filtering recommendation algorithm is to identify songs in the collection that a user is likely to enjoy, based on the other songs he/she listens to.

The *Million Song Dataset* (MSD) (Bertin-Mahieux et al. [1]) is a commonly used dataset in CF which contains user-item interaction data for around 380k songs and 1M users.

One of the most commonly used collaborative filtering algorithms is called *Matrix Factorization* (MF). This method aims to decompose the item-user matrix R into two separate matrices; one only encodes information about users, the other information about songs. The song-specific matrix $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{i \times D}$ can be viewed to contain D -dimensional song embeddings (called item-factors) for each song. A variant of this algorithm specialized for implicit feedback was proposed by Hu et al. [10]; this is one of the most commonly used approaches.

Vall et al. [31] modify standard implicit feedback matrix factorization to leverage knowledge from social tags. A dataset is used for which both user-interaction data and social tags are available, and a novel optimization technique is used to improve matrix factorization accuracy by incorporating the social tags. The tags are only used in the training process, and do not lead to additional functionality at test time.

Loepp et al. [19] show social tags can not only be used to improve the accuracy of matrix factorization techniques, but can also improve user satisfaction in recommender systems when they are used to interact with the system. Their algorithm is designed such that given the trained model, the user can assign importance weights to descriptive tags to influence recommendations. For example, a user's interaction data might have taught the model that he/she likes action, drama and horror

movies¹, but on a particular day, he/she is more interested in watching a horror movie. The user can then assign a high weight to the tags 'horror' and 'scary' to steer the model in the right direction. As large social tag datasets exist for music, this might be an interesting direction for music recommendation as well.

Tran et al. [30] propose an improvement on the existing Collaborative Metric Learning (CML) algorithm, which uses a metric learning approach to embed users and items in a joint latent space. The goal of the metric learning is to learn to embed songs, and users who are likely to enjoy them, close together and vice versa. In a recommendation use case, items can be retrieved by neighbour distance in the embedding space. The authors identify two problems with this approach: (1) it needs large batch sizes for good results (this limits scalability) (2) it is popularity biased (tends to recommend popular items). The contribution of this work is a sampling strategy for selecting negative samples, along with a loss function. The strategy consists of two parts: (1) a popularity-based sampling method to counteract popularity bias (2) the 2nd stage to allow for competitive results with much smaller batch sizes. The methodology is applied to datasets from three different domains, books, movies and music, and is shown to increase performance for all three. The improvement is greatest for music (MSD).

2.4 Hybrid Approaches

Motivated by the fact that collaborative filtering approaches have been shown to consistently outperform content-based approaches (Kim et al. [12]), and the fact that user-interaction data is much easier to collect than survey data, McFee [23] propose to use collaborative filtering/user-interaction data to optimize a content-based similarity model. A dataset of item-user interactions is used to create ranked lists of similar songs, under the assumption that if a large number of users listen to the same two songs, the songs must be similar. The proposed MLR algorithm is then optimized to predict these rankings from timbral features (vector-quantized MFCCs).

¹their model was trained on the MovieLens movie recommendation dataset

Van Den Oord et al. [32] combine CF- and content-based similarity learning by using a convolutional neural network (CNN) to predict item factor representations obtained using matrix factorization from mel-spectrograms, in an attempt to solve the cold-start problem that occurs in CF-based methods. They first show that the song vectors (called item factors in the paper) contain musically relevant information by successfully using them to predict descriptive tags (this task is discussed further in the next section). Then they show that when a CNN is used to predict these item-factors from audio, most of the user-item interactions can be reconstructed successfully. This means that their model is also able to recommend songs in a cold-start situation. This method is also shown to outperform MLR. Their work was one of the first to show that CNNs can be used to effectively extract information from (mel-)spectrograms.

Lee et al. [17] improve upon this result, by training a model that learns to predict user-item relevance scores directly, instead of reconstructing these scores using predicted item-factors. Similarly to Van Den Oord et al. [32], they use a CNN model that extracts features from mel-spectrograms.

2.5 Tag prediction

Tag prediction is a well-researched task within the field of MIR that aims to predict descriptive tags given only a song’s audio. These models are trained on datasets that contain both audio(-features) and tagging information, such as *MagnaTagATune* (MTT) (Law et al. [16]) and the *Million Song Dataset* (MSD) (Bertin-Mahieux et al. [1]). This task is relevant to our work for two reasons: (1) as Loepp et al. [19] have shown, tags are an effective means to increase user interaction in recommender models (2) tag prediction is a task that has led to many innovations in terms of neural network architectures for music.

Some notable works include (Kim et al. [13]), who introduced a convolutional neural network model that can effectively learn tag prediction from raw waveforms, (Pons et al. [25]) who showed that using musically motivated filter shapes in neural net-

works can improve learning on smaller datasets and (Won et al. [41]), who improved the interpretability of auto-tagging models by visualising self-attention weights in a transformer-like architecture.

2.6 Conclusions/Research direction

From the modest success of purely content-based approaches, and the apparent limitations in inter-user agreement, we conclude that algorithms trying to model some notion of "objective similarity" should not be the focus of future research. The fact that users do not generally agree on the similarity between different songs, shows that effective models should not try to "factor out" differences between users. Matrix factorization approaches use user-interaction data to extract models of users and of songs, capturing inter-user variation by design. The inherent cold-start problem that arises from the fact that user-interaction information is needed to construct a model of songs, can be alleviated by using a hybrid approach that also leverages content-based information. For this reason, we opt to experiment with the methodology proposed by Lee et al. [18] and compare it to other music recommendation systems. As the addition of tags could improve user interaction in (music) recommendation systems (see Loepp et al. [19]), we aim to combine similarity learning with tag prediction.

2.7 Research questions

Based on the work we reviewed, we formulate the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** Can we learn a shared feature representation from to effectively perform both similarity learning and tag prediction?
- **RQ2:** How can a music retrieval system be made to focus on relevant characteristics of music (genre, mood, instrumentation)?

Chapter 3

Methods

In this chapter, the technical concepts relevant to our methodology are explained. In sections 3.1-3.4 we explain techniques used in collaborative filtering (CF) based and content-based similarity algorithms. In section 3.5 and 3.6 we propose two systems to focus on relevant characteristics of music (genre, mood, instrumentation), in an attempt to answer **RQ2**.

3.1 Collaborative Filtering

For use with CF algorithms, user-item interactions such as *likes*, *plays* or *ratings* can be collected in a *user-item matrix*:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} & p_{13} & p_{14} \\ p_{21} & p_{22} & p_{23} & p_{24} \\ p_{31} & p_{32} & p_{33} & p_{34} \end{bmatrix}$$

where row i represents user i and column j represents item j . The *preference* values p_{ij} are usually integer values; binary in case it represents a like, integer when it represents play counts or a rating. In most cases, the matrix is very sparse, as *preference* values for most user-item pairs are unknown, so the remaining task is to predict unknown values.

3.1.1 Weighted Matrix Factorisation

Weighted matrix factorisation (WMF), as proposed by Hu et al. [9], is a modification of the traditional matrix factorisation algorithm. WMF is an algorithm used for implicit feedback models, which aims to decompose feedback of different users u and items i into independent user-factors x_u and item-factors y_i such that the preference of p_{ui} a user u for an item i can be represented as

$$\hat{p}_{ui} = x_u^T y_i \quad (3.1)$$

The *latent factors* x_u and y_i are D -dimensional vectors, where the dimensionality D is a parameter. Given an item's item-factors and m D -dimensional user-factors, we should be able to reconstruct each of the m users' preference for the item. The user-item preference is modeled as follows: given an *observation* r_{ui} , the preference p_{ui} is calculated as:

$$p_{ui} = \begin{cases} 1 & r_{ui} > 0 \\ 0 & r_{ui} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

The observations r_{ui} indicate how much of the item a user has consumed; if $r_{ui} = 0.5$, the user listened to 50% of the song and then skipped it. The preference p_{ui} formalises the notion that if a user u has played a song ($r_{ui} > 0$) we have an indication that u likes song i . Evidently, our confidence in the preference increases with r_{ui} - which is modeled as:

$$c_{ui} = 1 + \alpha \log(1 + r_{ui}/\epsilon) \quad (3.3)$$

Given these variables, the user-factors x_u and item-factors y_i are calculated using the objective function in formula 3.4. This modification of the regularised least-squares loss ensures that the preferences can be represented as $\hat{p}_{ui} = x_u^T y_i$ as accurately

as possible. The *latent factors* x_u and y_i are optimised alternating-least-squares (ALS) optimisation. This essentially involves alternatingly recalculating the user- and item-factors using the objective in formula 3.4.

$$\min_{x^*, y^*} \sum_{u,i} c_{ui} (p_{ui} - x_u^T y_i)^2 + \lambda \left(\sum_u \|x_u\|^2 + \sum_i \|y_i\|^2 \right) \quad (3.4)$$

In this work, we calculate user factors and item factors by applying WMF to a dataset of song-user play counts. The item factors y_i are used as a feature representation to find similarities between songs.

3.2 Feature Representation

Where analog sound is a *continuous* signal, it is stored digitally as a *discrete* signal. The values of the sound wave are measured at a certain *sampling frequency* and stored (see figure 1). Digital music typically has a sampling rate of 44,100 Hz, meaning that the signal contains 44,100 samples for each second. As the digital representation of sound files consists of thousands of floating point numbers indicating the sound wave's value at different time steps they are hard to interpret and take up a significant amount of memory. For this reason, sound and music data is usually converted to a different representation before being processed by MIR algorithms. This section describes how audio signals can be converted to an image-like feature representation.

3.2.1 Short-Time Fourier Transform

The Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) is a technique used to decompose an audio signal into the individual frequencies present at different time steps. The STFT results in a time-frequency representation of a signal by convolving it with a window function and calculating the regular Fourier Transform (FT) of the part that is selected by the window. The Fourier Transform converts the amplitude-time representation of an audio signal to a time-frequency representation - this shows

Figure 1: Illustration of a sampled sound wave. Taken from *Digital Audio 101: The Basics* [5]

the independent frequencies the sound consists of. The discrete STFT of a discrete signal $x(n)$ is calculated as:

$$\mathbf{STFT}\{x[n]\} \equiv X(m, k) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} x[n]w[n - m]e^{-j2\pi kn/N} \quad (3.5)$$

With n the (discrete) time index, m the position of the window function, k the discrete frequency index ¹ and N the width of the window the signal is convolved with. The STFT results in a complex-valued representation, that can be decomposed into a *magnitude* and *phase* for each time-frequency bin.

Given the magnitude and phase information of a signal, it can be transformed back to audio using the inverse STFT. However, phase information is usually discarded as only the magnitude-per-frequency information is used for most MIR applications.

Because the operation is applied to small overlapping windows, it allows one to observe time-dependent changes in frequency content. The magnitude information can be represented as a 2D image called a magnitude spectrogram, where one axis represents frequency (usually on the y-axis) and the other time (usually on the x-axis), where magnitude of each frequency bin is indicated using a colour. An example of a magnitude spectrogram is shown in figure 2. There are a couple of STFT hyperparameters that are often encountered in literature:

¹the discretization of time also results in discretization of frequency. Frequencies are represented as bins with index k and a width/resolution that depends on the sample rate and window size

- the *FFT size* or *n-FFT* is the length (in samples) of the window that the signal is convolved with,
- the *hop length* or *hop size* is the number of samples the window is shifted between steps when it is convolved with the signal. This distance determines the number of samples represented by a single time frame in the STFT (a single STFT frame is the outcome of applying the FT at one window location). When the hop length is chosen to be smaller than the FFT size, we end up with overlapping windows, which is often desirable
- the *window function* describes the shape of the window that the signal is multiplied with before the FT is applied.

These concepts are illustrated in figure 3

Figure 2: An example of a mel-spectrogram, with time on the horizontal axis, and frequency on the vertical axis. Magnitudes have been converted to decibels (dB), a logarithmic scale.

Figure 3: An illustration of the STFT operation, showing the meaning of various hyperparameters. Taken from the *MATLAB Documentation* [21]

Resolution issues The STFT has an important limitation: resolution in time and frequency are inversely related. These resolutions are determined by the width of the windowing function. A wide window gives a better frequency resolution (small differences between frequency components can be observed) but at the cost of poor time resolution. Conversely, a narrow window gives better time resolution (well-defined start and end of a signal), but poor frequency resolution.

3.2.2 Mel-Frequency

The Mel frequency scale aims to mimic the non-linear human ear perception of sound, by being more sensitive at lower frequencies and less sensitive at higher frequencies. By applying a set of triangular filters on the Mel-scale to the power (magnitude squared) spectrogram from STFT, one obtains a Mel-spectrogram. Mel-spectrograms are commonly used for machine learning tasks, like speech recognition, because they convert standard spectrograms to a representation that more accurately represents auditory perception of sound. By discarding irrelevant information

Mel-filtering results in a compressed representation of regular spectrograms, which facilitates processing with machine learning algorithms.

3.2.3 Log-compression

Spectrograms are often transformed using log-compression, which helps to balance the importance of detail in low and high energy regions of the spectrum. This technique is inspired by human hearing, as this also works roughly on a logarithmic scale, which means that humans can hear both really quiet and loud amplitudes. For this reason, sound pressure level or 'loudness' is measured using the logarithmic decibel (dB) scale. Log-compression is applied to a spectrogram \mathbf{H} using the following formula;

$$\mathbf{H}_{log} = \log(\alpha\mathbf{H} + \beta) \quad (3.6)$$

where the logarithm is applied element-wise. α and β are hyperparameters.

3.3 Applying Convolutional Neural Networks to Music

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been very successfully applied in multiple fields of machine learning, and work especially well for images, because their convolutional filters greatly reduce the number of parameters and naturally introduce *shift-invariance*, meaning that the model becomes insensitive to the location in an image a pattern occurs.

CNNs also work really well on magnitude spectrograms, as they are similar to images. However, an important difference with images is that the horizontal and vertical axes do not have the same meaning. For this reason, square kernels and two-dimensional convolutions are less suitable.

Furthermore, it is generally not desirable to have shift-invariance along the frequency axis, as in spectrograms, it does make a difference where on the frequency axis a

pattern occurs. Shifting a pattern along the frequency axis changes the frequency, noticeably changing the sound. For this reason, rectangular filters are often used in CNNs applied to spectrograms. Some works use filters that span the entire frequency axis and convolve only in the time-direction (Van Den Oord et al. [32], Lu et al. [20]) and others use rectangular filters of different sizes (Pons et al. [26]). Apart from this difference, CNN architectures for spectrograms are very similar to those used for computer vision tasks.

3.4 Metric Learning

As content-based approaches do not suffer from the cold-start problem, they could significantly improve user satisfaction for recommendation algorithms. Instead of using a hybrid content-based CF approach such as Van Den Oord et al. [32], one could apply *metric learning* to learn similarity between pairs of songs directly. Various approaches exist for training metric learning models, the most prominent being Siamese Networks (Koch et al. [15], Bromley et al. [2]) and Triplet Networks (Schroff et al. [27]). Both methods rely on the principle of *weight sharing* - reusing the same set of network parameters for multiple training instances and comparing their feature representations. A loss function is used that enforces the network to learn *discriminative* features.

The difference between the two methods is the way these features are learnt: Siamese networks process pairs of input samples, along with a label indicating if the samples are similar - so their feature representations should be pulled closer together, or dissimilar - so their feature representations should be pushed further apart. Triplet networks use triplets of samples - an *anchor*, *positive* and *negative* sample - and a loss function which forces the model to pull the anchor and positive's representations closer together, and the anchor and negative's further apart (see figure 4 for a visualisation).

The triplets should be selected so that the anchor and positive samples are similar, or from the same class, and the negative sample should be different, or at least less similar than the other two. The network is then trained to optimize the *triplet loss*:

Figure 4: Visualisation of distance learning in a triplet network. Taken from Schroff et al. [27]

$$\mathcal{L}_{triplet} = \max((d^+ - d^- + \alpha), 0) \quad (3.7)$$

Where $d^+ = \|\mathbf{f}^a - \mathbf{f}^p\|_2$ and $d^- = \|\mathbf{f}^a - \mathbf{f}^n\|_2$, are the L2-norms of the differences between the anchor's (\mathbf{f}^a), positive's (\mathbf{f}^p) and negative's (\mathbf{f}^n) feature vectors. This loss is minimized when the difference between d^+ and d^- is at least α . The α hyperparameter is called the *margin* and is used to ensure that the model does not learn to map all songs to the same embedding.

3.5 Directed similarity search

The goal of this work is to develop a music retrieval system that allows users to "direct" query-by-example search by focusing on different aspects of songs. Search for similar items is generally implemented as nearest-neighbour search in a space containing vector representation of items, using distance metrics such as the euclidean distance:

$$D(\mathbf{y}^i, \mathbf{y}^j) = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^D (\mathbf{y}_k^i - \mathbf{y}_k^j)^2} \quad (3.8)$$

with $\mathbf{y}^i, \mathbf{y}^j \in \mathbb{R}^D$ the vector representations for two items. The desired "directed search" could be achieved by assigning a higher weight to dimensions that describe relevant characteristics of a song, e.g. by applying weighted euclidean distance:

$$D(\mathbf{y}^i, \mathbf{y}^j) = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^D w_k (\mathbf{y}_k^i - \mathbf{y}_k^j)^2} \quad (3.9)$$

with w_k a per-dimensional weight that can be adjusted as desired. This distance metric has been used before in the machine learning literature: Wettschereck et al. [39] used it to improve the accuracy of a k-nearest-neighbour classification system, and Keogh et al. [11] used it to improve performance of a similarity search algorithm for time series data.

By using this metric to search for nearest neighbours, every aspect of a song that is encoded in its vector representation can be weighted individually. Evidently, in order to determine suitable values for w_k , we should identify what kind of characteristics are described by each of the dimensions in the song representations. In this work, we explore two possible methods: (1) post-hoc feature importance weighting (2) disentangled metric-learning. In the following two sections, these two methodologies will be described.

3.5.1 Post-hoc feature importance weighting

For this method, we first train a model to obtain song representations, and then (**post-hoc**) try to determine which characteristics are encoded in the different dimensions of the representations produced by this pre-trained model. This model can either be CF-based or content-based.

To determine the function of different features in the song representation, we train a logistic regression model on an auto-tagging task with the song representation as input (a multi-label classification problem). The probabilities for each of the tags is given by:

$$p(t_k) = \sigma\left(\sum_{j=1}^D w_{jk} y_j^i + b_k\right) \quad (3.10)$$

with $p(t_k)$ the probability for tag t_k , σ the sigmoid non-linearity function, $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times K}$ the weight matrix, and $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^K$ the bias vector. The weights w_{jk} can be viewed as importance weights of dimension j of the item factor \mathbf{y}^i for tag t_k . For example, if a particular dimension of the item-factors encodes information about the presence of

guitars, it might have a high weight for predicting the tag 'rock'. After training the logistic regression model, we can use its weights for evaluating the weighted euclidean distance in formula 3.9. Note that logistic regression weights can also attain negative values, indicating that features can also have an "inhibitory" function. For example, if a high value of a certain feature indicates the presence of vocals, it should lower the probability of predicting the tag 'instrumental'. In order to be able to use negative weights in the weighted euclidean distance, we take their absolute value. This should still lead to the desired behaviour: given a query song that has no vocals, if we search for similar songs in terms of 'instrumentalness', we would like to find candidate songs that have similar (low) values for the feature that encodes the presence of vocals.

3.5.2 Disentangled-metric learning

Instead of trying to determine the function of different features after training a feature extraction model (post-hoc), it might be wise to constrain the learned representations to separate different dimensions of variation. Such representations are called *disentangled*. For example, disentangled representations extracted from a dataset of handwritten digits, should separate information about the digit type from information about the rotation or the writing thickness (Chen et al. [3]). Thus, when varying the value(s) of the part of the representation that encodes rotation, the digit type and writing thickness should not change. This has two advantages: (1) when items can be compared in many different ways (e.g. color, shape, size) learning similarity is more well-defined if we do not try to quantify "general similarity", but rather "per-dimension" similarity (2) if we learn to embed these degrees of variation into separate spaces, we can focus on a single aspect when retrieving similar items. To this end, we adopt the metric learning approach used by Veit et al. [34] and Lee et al. [18]. This method uses a dataset of triplets $t^i = \{x_a^i, x_p^i, x_n^i | s(x_a, x_p) > s(x_a, x_n)\}$, with s the dimension along which the (musical) similarity is measured. A feature extractor is then trained using triplet loss (see formula 3.7) to learn to project items into an embedding space such that the triplet constraints are fulfilled. In order to ensure that the different dimensions of variation are separated in the learned representation, the

Figure 5: Illustration of the disentangled metric learning model. Taken from Lee et al. [18]

method uses a masking mechanism. The training set contains triplets based on different dimensions (*mood*, *genre*, *instrumentation* and *tempo* in the diagram). During training, when the a triplet for a certain dimension is encountered, only the values of a number of sub-dimensions in the representation are updated using backprop; the other dimensions in the representation are masked. As such, the distance between embeddings are calculated as $D(x_i, x_j; s) = \|f(x_i) \circ m_s - f(x_j) \circ m_s\|_2$, with m_s passing through only the subspace corresponding to similarity dimension s and \circ indicating elementwise multiplication. In this fashion, the different sub-dimensions should each capture only a single dimension of variation. An illustration of this method is shown in figure 5.

Lee et al. [18] applied this methodology to music similarity learning by sampling triplets based on the semantic tags in the MSD. They consider a pair of songs to be similar with respect to a certain dimension when they share at least one tag in that category. They use the 50 most used tags and follow the categorization proposed by Choi et al. [4]. The categories and their corresponding tags are shown in table 1.

As can be seen from table 1, not all tags are equally informative, and a couple of

Table 1: Categories for the top-50 tags in MSD, as proposed by Choi et al. [4].

Category	Corresponding tags in MSD
Era	'60s', '70s', '80s', '90s', '00s'
Genre	'indie pop', 'Hip-Hop', 'rnb', 'heavy metal', 'metal', 'jazz', 'acoustic', 'funk', 'pop', 'electro', 'Progressive rock', 'indie', 'electronica', 'blues', 'rock', 'experimental', 'classic rock', 'soul', 'House', 'alternative', 'folk', 'punk', 'alternative rock', 'hard rock', 'indie rock', 'electronic', 'dance', 'country'
Instrumentation	'instrumental', 'female vocalist', 'female vocalists', 'guitar', 'male vocalists'
Mood	'oldies', 'ambient', 'chillout', 'Mellow', 'party', 'beautiful', 'easy listening', 'chill', 'sad', 'sexy', 'catchy', 'happy'

(near) duplicates occur. For instance, including both 'female vocalist' and 'female vocalists' is not very useful. Furthermore, especially in the instrumentation category, there are a lot of essential tags missing ('piano' for instance), meaning that in terms of capturing instrumentation, our models will not be very detailed. This is a result of the fact that we use only the top-50 tags (as is common practice in other works). Although it might improve the usefulness of our system, we perform no further processing or selection of the tags.

Sampling strategy

It has been shown that the methodology for selecting negative and positive samples is an important factor for effectively training metric learning models (Manmatha et al. [22], Tran et al. [29]) We use a sampling strategy motivated from out-of-class negative sampling in Wang et al. [37]. To ensure that songs with less commonly occurring tags are sampled with the same probability, we use the following offline sampling process:

- Generate all possible tag pairs y_a and y_n which results in $n(n-1)$ pairs, where n is the number of tags. In our experiment, $n = 50$.
- Randomly sample 500 negative examples from the set of songs without anchor tag y_a but with a negative tag y_n . As a result, for each anchor tag, there y_a are $(n-1) \times 500$ negative examples.
- In case there are no items that fulfill the previous condition (tag y_n might be

a subset of the tag y_a), instead randomly select 500 songs without anchor tag y_a .

- During training, randomly select an anchor tag y_a . A positive example is sampled from the set of songs that have the tag y_a . The negative example is randomly sampled from the previously created pool of negative examples.

3.6 Feature extractor architectures

For our experiments, we compare different neural network architectures that serve as feature extractors. As a baseline, a pre-trained auto tagging model, is used as feature extractor. This model is the *short-chunk CNN* proposed in Won et al. [40], a 7-layer CNN with a fully-connected layer and residual connections. This architecture is a simple 2D CNN with 3×3 filters that is trained on short chunks of audio: its inputs are chunks of 3.69s of audio (59,049 samples @ 16 kHz) that are converted to mel-spectrograms on-the-fly. The activations of the penultimate layer of the network are used as "tagging embedding". Additionally, for the disentangled metric learning model, we use the inception-architecture proposed in Lee et al. [18].

In table 2 below, the inception architecture is described. The inception blocks used in the architecture are "naive inception modules" as described by Szegedy et al. [28]. As shown in figure 6, the inception module consists of a concatenation of three convolutional layers with different kernel sizes and a 3×3 max pooling layer. Since the outputs are concatenated in the filter/channel dimension, using 64 filters for each of the four layers results in an output size of 256 in the filter dimension. Similarly to the short-chunk CNN architecture it uses 4.13s chunks of audio (66,150 samples @ 16kHz) that are converted to mel-spectrograms on-the-fly.

For both architectures, songs are split into chunks at test-time, and fed into the model by stacking chunks in the batch dimension. The embeddings for all chunks of a song are aggregated by computing the mean.

Figure 6: A "naive" inception module. Taken from Szegedy et al. [28]

Table 2: The feature extractor architecture as proposed by Lee et al. [18]. The layers labeled as "inception#" are naive inception modules as shown in figure 6.

Layer	Number of filters	Filter size	Stride	Padding	Output size
input	-	-	-	-	$N \times 128 \times 130$
conv1	64	5×5	1×1	2×2	$N \times 64 \times 128 \times 129$
max-pool	-	2×2	2×2	-	$N \times 64 \times 64 \times 64$
inception1	256	-	2×2	-	$N \times 256 \times 32 \times 32$
inception2	256	-	2×2	-	$N \times 256 \times 16 \times 16$
inception3	256	-	2×2	-	$N \times 256 \times 8 \times 8$
inception4	256	-	2×2	-	$N \times 256 \times 4 \times 4$
inception5	256	-	2×2	-	$N \times 256 \times 2 \times 2$
inception6	256	-	2×2	-	$N \times 256 \times 1 \times 1$
inception7	256	-	1×1	-	$N \times 256 \times 1 \times 1$

Chapter 4

Experiments & Results

In this section, we perform experiments to optimise and compare the methods introduced in section 3.5. Firstly, the dataset used for the experiments is described. In sections 4.2 and 4.3, we perform experiments to develop the two proposed models. In sections 4.4 and 4.5 we quantitatively evaluate different variants of the proposed models. Finally, in section 4.6, we use retrieval examples and visualisations to qualitatively compare the proposed models.

4.1 Datasets

The dataset used for our experiments is constructed by combining different subsets of the Million Song Dataset (MSD) (Bertin-Mahieux et al. [1]). Specifically, we use a subset of the Last.FM dataset, which contains semantic tags for 280,471 songs. We use a filtered version, using only songs longer than 29 seconds, following Kim et al. [13]. Following Choi et al. [4], we only use the 50 most used tags. Additionally, we require the song-user interaction data in the Echonest Taste Profile Subset, for 384,546 songs. As we require both sources of information for our experiments, we'll be working with the songs that are contained within both subsets: this leaves 154,235 songs.

4.2 Tag prediction performance

As the weights of the logistic regression model are an essential component of the feature weighting methodology, we first evaluate how this model performs on top-50 tag prediction. The logistic regression classifier uses WMF item-factors as features. We train the model using 10-fold cross validation (following Van Den Oord et al. [32]) and the Adam optimizer (Kingma et al. [14]). In table 3, we compare results on different subsets of the dataset .

Table 3: Tag prediction performance for logistic regression models with WMF item embeddings as features. Scores are calculated by averaging over over all top-50 tags first, and then averaging over 10 folds.

Subset	AUC
All	0.736 \pm 0.002
10,000 most popular	0.816 \pm 0.004
10,000 least popular	0.538 \pm 0.003

The results in this experiment provide an answer to **RQ1**: the song representations learned using WMF can also be used to perform tag prediction. The results show that the performance using only the 10,000 most popular songs gives better performance than using all songs. We conjecture that there are two possible explanations for this behaviour:

1. The tag distribution the top 10,000 songs is skewed: they have less of the tags that are harder to predict.
2. The item embeddings for top-10,000 songs contain more useful information (because more people listened to them)

In order to test which of the two explanations is true, we also train a model on the 10,000 least popular songs. The fact that the model trained on this subset gives even worse performance shows that the second explanation is most likely the most important factor, although the first explanation could also contribute to the observed behaviour.

4.3 Disentangled Metric Learning

In order to use disentangled embeddings for refined search, we first try to reproduce the model proposed by Lee et al. [18]. The model is trained using triplets for each of the similarity dimensions (era, genre, instrument, mood). Lee et al. [18] evaluate the quality of the model using triplet prediction accuracy - they test how often the model maps the anchor and positive items in a test triplet closer together than the anchor and the negative. We compare our results to the results reported in the original paper in table 4.

Table 4: Triplet prediction results for disentangled metric learning model. Accuracies using only the (disentangled) subdimensions are compared to using all dimensions of the learned embeddings.

Used space	Era	Genre	Instrument	Mood
All dimensions	0.680	0.693	0.586	0.632
Sub-dimensions	0.730	0.741	0.692	0.673
All dimensions (in Lee et al. [18])	-	0.708	0.657	0.717
Sub-dimensions (in Lee et al. [18])	-	0.785	0.798	0.790

Following Lee et al. [18], we compare triplet prediction accuracies obtained when using only the relevant sub-dimensions for distance evaluation, to using all dimensions of the embeddings. In line with their results, using only the relevant sub-dimensions increases accuracy for all categories. However, we observe that the results are not as good as reported in the original paper. This could have two reasons:

1. Due to computational limitations, we constructed the triplets used for training from a smaller subset of songs ($\sim 20k$ unique songs vs. $\sim 200k$ unique songs). This results in a very small number of unique songs for less-used tag categories (mood, instrument, era) and might cause worse performance. Although a smaller number of unique songs were used, we used the same number of triplets (40k per category).
2. Lee et al. [18] might have used a different strategy for sampling negatives; the methodology used in the paper is not explicitly mentioned. We sampled

negatives using the methodology explained in section 3.5.2.

Although our results are not as good as those reported by Lee et al. [18], we assume our model is sufficient to be used for further experiments.

4.4 General recommendation performance

In order to assess how well different song embeddings correlate with the listening behaviour in the EchoNest Taste Profile subset and thus how well the embeddings can be used for recommendation, the embeddings were used to reconstruct user-song play counts. By initialising the song factors y_i in formula 3.4 with pre-calculated song embeddings and keeping them fixed in the optimization procedure, the song-user play counts can be approximated by calculating the user factors. This modification turns the ALS optimization procedure into a regression problem. The quality of the reconstruction is evaluated by calculating the AUC for binary user-song interaction classification, as well as the mean average precision (mAP) for the ranked song recommendations for each user. The results for different song embedding variants are shown in table 5

Table 5: Recommendation/user-song interaction reconstruction performance for different song embedding types. AUC evaluates how well the different song embeddings can be used for binary interaction prediction, and mAP measures how well the ranked song recommendation for users agree with their listening behaviour.

Song representation	AUC	mAP
WMF item-factors	0.953	0.34
Disentangled embeddings	0.901	0.144
Auto-tagging embeddings	0.824	0.060
Random	0.752	0.064

The results show that WMF gives by far the best recommendation performance - which makes sense as the objective directly optimizes reconstruction of listening behaviour. Furthermore, it is interesting to see that randomly sampled song embeddings still result in a reasonable AUC score - this shows that using separate user and song factors/embeddings gives a lot of flexibility and that by only optimizing

one of the two, the listening behaviour can already be reconstructed to some extent. The other two compared methods are (1) embeddings produced by a pre-trained auto-tagging model (provided by Won et al. [40]) (2) the embeddings produced by the disentangled metric learning model. The performance for the auto-tagging embedding is slightly better than the randomly initialised song embeddings in terms of AUC, but worse in terms of mAP. This shows that the representations learned by the auto-tagging model do not correlate well with the listening behaviour in the dataset. Remarkably, the results for the disentangled embeddings are significantly better than the auto-tagging embeddings (9.3% improvement in AUC, 140% improvement in mAP), although the learning procedure is also based on tags. Given these results, the disentangled metric learning model seems promising for (content-based) recommendation.

4.5 Directed search performance

Keeping in mind that the goal of this work is to design a query-by-example retrieval system that can focus on different aspects of the query song, we would like to evaluate how well the two proposed methods work for this use case. However, since the similarity of two songs (in some dimension of similarity) is a highly subjective matter (Flexer et al. [8], Flexer et al. [7]), only a user study could truly provide insight into the effectiveness of the methods. Due to the time constraints of this study, we opted to use a different type of evaluation: we use tag co-occurrence as an indication of similarity between songs. For example, if the query song has the tag 'guitar', and we choose to focus on its instrumentation, we consider retrieved songs to be relevant if they share the same tag 'guitar'. Note that if two songs share the same tag 'guitar', this does not necessarily mean that the guitar parts are similar. As such, the evaluation methodology is severely limited, but we hope it will still provide some insight into the differences between algorithms.

Where feature-weighting is used to focus on a single tag, disentangled embeddings can only be used to focus on a tag category (era, mood, genre, instrumentation). For this reason, the evaluation metrics are calculated in a different manner. For the

feature-weighting methodology, the per-tag-category metrics are calculated using algorithm 1. For the disentangled embedding methodology, the procedure to find the ranking of k nearest neighbours is different: instead of using per-tag weights applied to the song, this method uses the sub-dimension that the desired query tag belongs to to find nearest neighbours.

```

Data: song tags, song embeddings, tag importance weights, tag categories
precisions = [], [], [], [] /* empty list for each tag category */
maps = [], [], [], [] /* empty list for each tag category */
for song in songs do
  for tag in songTags[song] do
    relevances = []
    category = tagCategories[tag]
    weightedEmb = songEmbs[song]  $\odot$  tagImpWeights[tag]
    ranking = NNb(weightedEmb, k=500) /* find k nearest
      neighbours of embedding */
    for rank, recSong in ranking do
      if tag in songTags[recSong] then
        | relevances.append(1)
      else
        | relevances.append(0)
      end
    end
    songPrecision = precision(relevances)
    songMap = map(relevances)
    precisions[category].append(songPrecision)
    maps[category].append(song map)
  end
end
return mean(precisions), mean(maps) /* calculate per-category
  means for precision an map arrays */

```

Algorithm 1: How to calculate the mAP@k and precision@k for the different tag categories, under the feature weighting methodology

In tables 6 and 7 we show the tag co-occurrence results for two baselines (top sub-table) and different variants of the two proposed methods (bottom sub-table). For an honest comparison between the content-based disentangled embeddings model and the CF-based WMF models, we calculate metrics for both the cold-start and warm-start settings. To clarify, warm-start indicates that we evaluate the models on the subset of songs that the metric learning model was trained on, and cold-start only on unseen songs. This distinction is necessary as WMF cannot be applied in a cold-start setting (it always requires usage information to recommend a song).

Table 6: Warm-start tag co-occurrence performance for the two proposed methods and standard WMF. Precision (P@k) and mean average precision (mAP) are calculated by cutting off at k=500 recommendations. Metrics calculated on the songs in the training set of the DEMB model

Method	Era		Genre		Instrumentation		Mood		Overall	
	P@k	mAP	P@k	mAP	P@k	mAP	P@k	mAP	P@k	mAP
WMF	0.069	0.106	0.165	0.22	0.078	0.106	0.062	0.093	0.122	0.167
Tagging embeddings	0.042	0.054	0.098	0.112	0.062	0.075	0.042	0.055	0.075	0.089
WMF + feature weighting	0.062	0.096	0.171	0.229	0.079	0.108	0.062	0.094	0.125	0.171
Tagging embeddings + feature weighting	0.039	0.049	0.118	0.138	0.051	0.065	0.069	0.098	0.09	0.11
Disentangled embeddings (Subdims)	0.069	0.085	0.14	0.162	0.072	0.086	0.071	0.087	0.109	0.128
Disentangled embeddings (All dims)	0.067	0.084	0.146	0.167	0.076	0.092	0.069	0.085	0.112	0.131

Table 7: Cold start tag co-occurrence performance for the two proposed methods and standard WMF. Precision (P@k) and mean average precision (mAP) are calculated by cutting off at 500 recommendations. Metrics calculated on the songs not present in the training set of the DEMB model

Method	Era		Genre		Instrumentation		Mood		Overall	
	P@k	mAP	P@k	mAP	P@k	mAP	P@k	mAP	P@k	mAP
WMF	0.052	0.093	0.162	0.223	0.08	0.116	0.044	0.085	0.133	0.189
Tagging embeddings	0.025	0.037	0.097	0.111	0.058	0.071	0.021	0.034	0.08	0.094
WMF + feature weighting	0.048	0.086	0.172	0.236	0.087	0.123	0.045	0.093	0.141	0.198
Tagging embeddings + feature weighting	0.025	0.053	0.11	0.122	0.047	0.072	0.037	0.055	0.09	0.105
Disentangled embeddings (Subdims)	0.045	0.061	0.144	0.168	0.068	0.083	0.053	0.074	0.12	0.142
Disentangled embeddings (All dims)	0.046	0.064	0.15	0.173	0.075	0.092	0.047	0.07	0.124	0.146

From the results in tables 6 and 7, we make the following observations:

- Feature weighting (FW) improves overall performance for both baselines: +3.6% mAP +4.1% P@k for WMF, +17% mAP +8.6% P@k for tagging.¹
- CF-based WMF outperforms content-based disentangled embeddings in both cold-start and warm-start settings.
- WMF + FW gives best overall performance, but is outperformed by standard WMF for the 'era' category
- The disentangled embeddings (DEMB) method greatly outperforms the tagging embedding baseline.
- DEMB performs similarly on cold-start data as it does on warm-start data

4.6 Qualitative evaluation

In evaluating recommendation systems, evaluation metrics alone do not give much insight. To get a better idea about what differences exist between the different methods, we conduct two experiments to qualitatively compare our two proposed methods against standard WMF.

4.6.1 Retrieval demonstration

In order to simulate the use of the different system in a query-by-example retrieval setting, we select a query track for a tag from each of the tag categories (genre, mood, instrumentation, era) and find the 10 most similar tracks according to each of the three systems. The following tags were selected: 'House' (genre), 'female vocalists' (instrumentation), 'chill' (mood), '60s' (era). The subset of songs used for recommendation are unseen by the DEMB model; it is a cold-start setting. The retrieval results for the tagging embeddings can be found in the appendix.

¹Scores were averaged over the cold-start and warm-start subsets.

Tag: 'House' (genre)

Table 8: Standard WMF results for the tag 'House' (genre)

Song	Tags
Armand Van Helden & A-TRAK Present Duck Sauce - aNYway	'soul', 'acoustic', 'funk', 'House'
Nelly Furtado - In God's Hands	'pop'
Stardust - Music Sounds Better With You (12" Club Mix)	'electronic', 'dance', 'House'
Crystal Waters - Gypsy Woman (She's Homeless)	'dance', '90s', 'party', 'House'
Nightcrawlers - Push The Feeling On	'dance', '90s', 'House'
Underworld - Born Slippy	'electronic', 'dance'
Mylo - Drop The Pressure	'electronic', 'dance', 'House'
2 Unlimited - Get Ready For This	'dance', '90s'
Dirty Vegas - Days Go By	'electronic', 'dance', 'House'
Jamiroquai - Little L	'dance', 'funk'
The Sugarhill Gang - Rapper's Delight	'80s', 'Hip-Hop'

Table 9: FW-WMF results for the tag 'House' (genre)

Song	Tags
Armand Van Helden & A-TRAK Present Duck Sauce - aNYway	'soul', 'acoustic', 'funk', 'House'
Stardust - Music Sounds Better With You (12" Club Mix)	'electronic', 'dance', 'House'
Nightcrawlers - Push The Feeling On	'dance', '90s', 'House'
Crystal Waters - Gypsy Woman (She's Homeless)	'dance', '90s', 'party', 'House'
Mylo - Drop The Pressure	'electronic', 'dance', 'House'
The Sugarhill Gang - Rapper's Delight	'80s', 'Hip-Hop'
Underworld - Born Slippy	'electronic', 'dance'
Fake Blood - I Think I Like It	'electronic', 'dance', 'House'
Nelly Furtado - In God's Hands	'pop'
Calvin Harris - I'm Not Alone	'electronic', 'dance', 'House'
CSS - Music Is My Hot, Hot Sex (Album)	'indie', 'electronic', 'electro'

Table 10: Disentangled Embeddings results for the tag 'House' (genre)

Song	Tags
Armand Van Helden & A-TRAK Present Duck Sauce - aNYway	'soul', 'acoustic', 'funk', 'House'
Miley Cyrus - Hoedown Throwdown	'pop', 'dance', 'country'
DJ Laz - Move Shake Drop Remix	'dance'
Rev19n - Someone Like You	'indie', 'electronic', 'electronica'
Prince & The Revolution - Kiss (LP Version)	'rock', 'pop', 'soul', '80s', 'funk'
Lupe Fiasco feat. Biship G and Nikki Jean - Little Weapon	'pop', 'Hip-Hop'
Black Eyed Peas / Justin Timberlake - My Style	'dance', 'Hip-Hop'
Mystikal featuring Nivea - Danger (Been So Long)	'Hip-Hop'
The Notorious B.I.G. - Who Shot Ya	'Hip-Hop'
Big Punisher featuring Joe - Still Not A Player	'Hip-Hop'
Fatboy Slim - Champion Sound	'electronic'

As we can see in table 8, standard WMF already mostly retrieves songs that share the same genre tag ('House') as the query song. As we will see in section 4.6.2, WMF tends to cluster songs with the same genre. However, there are some misses: the highest ranked song is a slow pop song, that should not have been retrieved for a the query 'House'. The last two results are disco/funk songs with electronic influences which are quite similar to the query song, so we will consider them as a correct retrievals, even though they do not have the tag 'House'. 7 out of 10 songs retrieved by the feature weighted WMF system were also retrieved by the standard WMF system - the results are not much different although the ranking order is different. An improvement is that the Nelly Furtado song is ranked on the 8th place instead of the first. The last result however, we consider a miss, since it is far too slow to be labeled as a 'House' song. The results for the disentangled embedding system are significantly worse: for some reason, it retrieves multiple songs labeled as 'Hip-Hop' - a genre with a far slower and different rhythm. Perhaps this behaviour would not have occurred if we also sampled triplets based on tempo, as done by Lee et al. [18]. The first retrieved song also is far from a 'House' song. Overall, we can see that the results correspond well with the quantitative evaluation in tables 6 and 7 (which makes sense as we are mostly relying on tag co-occurrence in this qualitative evaluation).

Tag: 'female vocalists' (instrumentation)

Table 11: Standard WMF results for tag 'female vocalists' (instrumentation)

Song	Tags
Stevie Nicks & Don Henley - Leather And Lace	'rock', 'female vocalists', 'classic rock', '80s'
Stevie Nicks - Stand Back	'female vocalists', 'classic rock', '80s'
Elton John - Sad Songs (Say So Much)	'rock', 'pop', 'classic rock', '80s'
Gerry Rafferty - Right Down The Line	'classic rock', '70s'
Crosby, Stills & Nash - Southern Cross	'Mellow', '70s'
38 Special - Caught Up In You	'classic rock', '80s'
Journey - Who's Cryin' Now	'classic rock', '80s'
Heart - Magic Man	'classic rock'
Ambrosia - How Much I Feel	'70s'
Little River Band - Lonesome Loser	'classic rock', '70s'
The Motels - Only The Lonely	'80s'

Table 12: FW-WMF results for tag 'female vocalists' (instrumentation)

Song	Tags
Stevie Nicks & Don Henley - Leather And Lace	'rock', 'female vocalists', 'classic rock', '80s'
Crosby, Stills & Nash - Southern Cross	'Mellow', '70s'
Bruce Springsteen - I'm On Fire	'rock', 'classic rock', '80s'
Gerry Rafferty - Right Down The Line	'classic rock', '70s'
The Blues Brothers - Groove Me (Live Version)	'blues'
Boston - Amanda	'rock', 'classic rock', '80s'
Fleetwood Mac - Go Your Own Way (LP Version)	'rock', 'classic rock', '70s'
Billy Squier - My Kinda Lover	'rock', 'classic rock', '80s'
Stevie Nicks - Stand Back	'female vocalists', 'classic rock', '80s'
Heart - Magic Man	'classic rock'
Heart - Crazy On You	'rock', 'female vocalists', 'classic rock'

Table 13: Disentangled Embeddings results for tag 'female vocalists' (instrumentation)

Song	Tags
Stevie Nicks & Don Henley - Leather And Lace	'rock', 'female vocalists', 'classic rock', '80s'
She & Him - Sentimental Heart	'indie', 'folk', 'female vocalist'
Sia - Soon We'll Be Found	'indie', 'female vocalists', 'beautiful', 'chillout'
India.Arie - Beautiful	'female vocalists', 'soul'
Feist - Gatekeeper	'indie', 'female vocalists'
Taylor Swift - Crazier	'pop', 'country'
Michelle Shocked - Quality Of Mercy	'female vocalists', 'blues'
Camera Obscura - James	'pop', 'alternative', 'female vocalists'
Tori Amos - Precious Things	'alternative', 'female vocalists'
Laura Pausini - Gente	'pop', 'female vocalists'
THE CHIFFONS - One Fine Day	'oldies', '60s'

For the tag 'female vocalists' the differences between the WMF-based algorithms and the disentangled embeddings method are very clear: the WMF-based algorithms tend to group together songs of the same genre, but are agnostic of the gender of the vocalists. This is caused by the fact that female vocalists are not necessarily associated with particular genres; if we would have queried for the tag 'guitar', most likely all of the retrieved songs would have featured a guitar (as guitars are very typical for rock music). Manual evaluation revealed that the songs by Heart and The Motels also have a female vocalist, although they are not labeled as such; this results in 3 out of the 10 songs recommended by standard WMF featuring female vocalists (all of which were also retrieved by feature-weighted WMF), 4 out of 10 for feature-weighted WMF. For the disentangled embeddings method, all of the retrieved songs are tagged as having 'female vocalists'. In contrast to the two WMF-based algorithms, the disentangled embeddings algorithm retrieves songs of multiple different genres. Manual evaluation of the songs revealed that the singing styles are similar overall, although there are some songs that do not seem to fit as well.

Tag: 'chill' (mood)

Table 14: Standard WMF results for tag 'chill' (mood)

Song	Tags
Donavon Frankenreiter - Day Dreamer	'rock', 'Mellow', 'folk', 'chill', 'acoustic'
Donavon Frankenreiter - It Don't Matter	'chill', 'acoustic'
Matt Wertz - Wade Through The Night	'indie', 'folk', 'chill'
Jack Johnson - Holes To Heaven	'chill', 'acoustic'
Jack Johnson - Moonshine	'acoustic'
Jack Johnson - Gone	'Mellow', 'acoustic'
Jack Johnson - Cocoon	'Mellow', 'acoustic'
Jack Johnson - Dreams Be Dreams	'acoustic'
Jack Johnson - The Horizon Has Been Defeated	'acoustic'
Jack Johnson - Fortunate Fool	'chill', 'acoustic'
Jack Johnson - You And Your Heart	'rock', 'pop'

Table 15: FW-WMF results for tag 'chill' (mood)

Song	Tags
Donavon Frankenreiter - Day Dreamer	'rock', 'Mellow', 'folk', 'chill', 'acoustic'
G. Love & Special Sauce - Baby's Got Sauce	'Mellow', 'chill', 'blues'
Jack Johnson - Holes To Heaven	'chill', 'acoustic'
Blur - Sing	'rock'
Jack Johnson - Taylor	'chill', 'acoustic'
Empire Of The Sun - The World	'indie', 'electronic'
Matt Wertz - Wade Through The Night	'indie', 'folk', 'chill'
Empire Of The Sun - Tiger By My Side	'electronic'
MGMT - Future Reflections	'alternative', 'indie', 'electronic'
M.I.A. - Galang	'electronic', 'dance', 'Hip-Hop'
Architecture In Helsinki - Do the whirlwind	'indie', 'indie pop'

Table 16: Disentangled Embeddings results for tag 'chill' (mood)

Song	Tags
Donavon Frankenreiter - Day Dreamer	'rock', 'Mellow', 'folk', 'chill', 'acoustic'
John Mayer - Back To You	'rock', 'pop'
Tristan Prettyman feat. Jason Mraz - Shy That Way	'acoustic'
Jason Mraz - No Doubling Back	'acoustic'
Jamie Cullum - Don't Stop The Music	'jazz'
Lykke Li - Everybody But Me	'indie', 'electronic', 'female vocalists'
Train - Drops Of Jupiter	'rock', 'pop', 'alternative'
Elvis Perkins In Dearland - Hey	'beautiful', 'chill', 'sad'
Blitzen Trapper - Black River Killer (Album)	'indie', 'folk'
Jarabe De Palo - Agua	'pop'
Incubus - Are You In?	'rock', 'alternative', 'alternative rock'

If we consider 'Mellow' as a synonym of 'chill', then WMF results in 5 relevant retrievals out of 10. Clearly, WMF offers a low level of variation, as many of the retrieved songs are by the same artist. Arguably, all of the retrieved songs by Jack Johnson could be labeled as 'chill'. Feature-weighted WMF retrieves 4 relevant songs, offers more variation, but also has more misses: *M.I.A. - galang* is (arguably) too 'party' to be labeled as 'chill'. Overall, the meaning of 'chill' does not seem to be captured as well as 'House' or 'female vocalists'. This is probably caused by the fact that mood tags are not as clearly defined as instrumentation- or genre tags, and more open to subjective interpretation. The disentangled embeddings system seems to only retrieve a single relevant song. However, manual inspection showed that there are other songs that could be considered as relevant (e.g. *Lykke Li - Everybody But Me*); another seemingly obvious miss (*Incubus - Are You In?*) actually fits quite well - it is a mellow rock song that features chill sections. Overall inspection reveals that although not many results share the same tag, retrieved songs match query song quite well (subjective of course)

Tag: '60s' (era)

Table 17: Standard WMF results for tag '60s' (era)

Song	Tags
Bob Dylan - Like A Rolling Stone	'rock', 'classic rock', 'folk', '60s'
Johnny Kidd & The Pirates - Shakin' All Over	'60s'
Tommy James And The Shondells - Hanky Panky	'oldies', '60s'
Bob Dylan - Just Like A Woman	'classic rock', 'folk'
Beyoncé - At Last	'female vocalists', 'soul', 'rnb'
Janis Joplin - Me And Bobby McGee	'female vocalists', 'classic rock', '60s'
The Doors - People Are Strange	'rock', 'classic rock', '60s'
Cream - Crossroads	'rock', 'classic rock', 'blues'
The Blues Brothers - Jailhouse Rock	'blues'
Joe Cocker - With A Little Help From My Friends	'rock', 'classic rock'
Tom Petty - Saving Grace (Album Version)	'rock', 'classic rock'

Table 18: FW-WMF results for tag '60s' (era)

Song	Tags
Bob Dylan - Like A Rolling Stone	'rock', 'classic rock', 'folk', '60s'
Johnny Kidd & The Pirates - Shakin' All Over	'60s'
Tommy James And The Shondells - Hanky Panky	'oldies', '60s'
Eels - Novocaine For The Soul	'rock', 'alternative', 'indie', 'indie rock'
The Bravery - Time Won't Let Me Go	'rock', 'alternative', 'indie'
Percy Sledge - When A Man Loves A Woman	'soul', 'oldies', '60s'
The Thrills - Big Sur	'indie'
Beyoncé - At Last	'female vocalists', 'soul', 'rnb'
The White Stripes - Hotel Yorba	'rock', 'alternative', 'indie'
Bob Dylan - Just Like A Woman	'classic rock', 'folk'
The Doors - People Are Strange	'rock', 'classic rock', '60s'

Table 19: Disentangled Embeddings results for tag '60s' (era)

Song	Tags
Bob Dylan - Like A Rolling Stone	'rock', 'classic rock', 'folk', '60s'
Matt Costa - Miss Magnolia	'folk', 'acoustic'
Creedence Clearwater Revival - Run Through The Jungle	'classic rock'
Kansas - Dust in The Wind	'classic rock', '70s'
Devendra Banhart - Be Kind	'indie', 'folk', 'chill'
The Pogues - The Body Of An American	'punk'
Peter Sarstedt - Where Do You Go To (My Lovely)	'folk', 'oldies', '60s'
The Ventures - Surf Rider (Instrumental) (Stereo)	'instrumental'
Stone Temple Pilots - Plush (Acoustic)	'rock', 'acoustic'
Bee Gees - Run To Me	'pop', 'oldies', '70s'
Gilbert O'Sullivan", 'Alone Again (Naturally)	'70s'

The retrieval of the era tag '60s' seems to indicate superiority of the WMF system. WMF retrieves 5 relevant songs. An interesting example is the appearance of the Beyoncé song. It seems to be an irrelevant song, but it turns out to be a cover of a 60s song that features typical instrumentation. The same relevant songs retrieved by WMF are also retrieved by feature-weighted WMF. Disentangled does less well it only retrieves 2 relevant songs (*The Ventures - Surf Rider* was found out also to be from the 60s), apparently it has a hard time to differentiate between 60s and 70s songs from the audio itself.

4.6.2 T-sne visualisation of song embeddings

In the second qualitative experiment, a dimensionality reduction technique called t-SNE (Van Der Maaten et al. [33]) is used to visualise the high-dimensional song embeddings. The two-dimensional representation produced by t-SNE will give insight into the clustering behaviour of the different methods. In the visualisations, we use genre tags to differentiate between different types of songs. The other tag categories were not used in the t-SNE plots, as mood, instrumentation and era tags are too scarce to obtain a large enough set of songs for visualisation.

Figure 7 visualises the item factor embeddings learned by WMF. We can see that compact clusters are formed that mostly group together songs of the same genre. There are areas that are less isolated, but the overall structure is clearly visible.

Figure 7: T-SNE visualisation of WMF embeddings

The visualisation in figure 8 shows that the disentangled embeddings method also does a fairly good job at mapping songs with the same genre close together. The clusters are not nearly as compact as those produced by WMF, but the "Hip-Hop"

and "dance" clusters are quite well-defined. The "pop" and "rock" clusters are a lot more messy than those produced by WMF.

Figure 8: T-SNE visualisation of disentangled embeddings (genre sub-dimension)

The embeddings produced by the tagging model (figure 9) do not seem to show any structure. It is unclear how a state-of-the-art tagging model can perform well at tag prediction while displaying so little structure in the embeddings. These results do agree well with the recommendation results in table 5 and the tag co-occurrence performance in tables 6 and 7.

Figure 9: T-SNE visualisation of tagging embeddings

Chapter 5

Discussion

The quantitative and qualitative evaluations we have performed have shown that the content-based disentangled embedding method is unable to outperform the weighted matrix factorisation (WMF) method, which is the most popular algorithm for (music) recommender systems. As we have seen, WMF automatically groups together songs with similar semantic tags; this is caused by the fact that by users tend to listen specific types of music, or listen to multiple songs from the same artist (who tend to stick to a certain sound). It is noteworthy that in some cases the performance of the disentangled embeddings system comes quite close to WMF, as its content-based nature means that it does not require usage information to recommend songs. The fact that its performance for unseen songs is similar to its performance for songs from the training set, shows that it does not suffer from the *cold-start problem*: it is able to recommend new and unpopular songs. Also, the fact that the content-based method has access to song audio, means that it could lead to improved performance when focusing on the 'instrumentation' aspect of a song. However, since we only used the top-50 most popular tags, the available 'instrumentation' tags are not very informative (see table 1) as the tag 'piano' for instance is not used.

Although our evaluation methods mainly focused on "objective" song similarity and tag co-occurrence, the recommendation experiment in table 5 shows that the disentangled embeddings are also suitable for personalised recommendation that

takes into account inter-user differences. This can be achieved by calculating user factors using WMF while keeping the item factors (initialised as disentangled song embeddings) fixed.

However, the fact that it cannot outperform WMF, is an indication that usage data contains essential information that cannot (easily) be extracted from audio (which has been shown often in previous work such as Kim et al. [12]). It might be desirable to re-evaluate the differences between WMF and disentangled embeddings after improving the quality of the disentangled embeddings by using more data and also including tempo/bpm metadata, as Lee et al. [18] did (see section 4.3).

Furthermore, our proposed method feature-weighting method improves performance in almost all cases, except for "era" retrieval. This is remarkable, as previous work has shown that "era" tags can be predicted with high accuracy (Choi et al. [4]). Perhaps this means that predicting era tags uses information from many different parts of the embedding, and forcing it to focus on a part of the embedding causes it to lose valuable information (this could mean that "era" is characterised by a combination of genre, instrumentation and mood). Although Feature-weighted WMF gives best performance, it only gives a slight improvement over standard WMF (+3.6% mAP +4.1% P@k).

Finally, it must be noted that our evaluation methodology is fairly flawed. Although the Tag co-occurrence analysis brought to light some differences between methods, it does not give insight into what we desire to achieve with our system. If we want to answer the question "are the retrieved songs similar in mood to the query song?", a user experiment is necessary. Even though users most likely won't unanimously agree about the similarity of different songs (Flexer et al. [8]) this will be a far more realistic evaluation of how the proposed systems behave.

Chapter 6

Conclusions & Future work

6.1 Conclusions

The aim of this thesis was to develop a query-by-example system that can focus on specific aspects of a query song, such as 'instrumentation', 'mood', 'era' or 'genre', thus increasing user control. To this end, we compared two methods: (1) a feature-weighting method, that places higher weight on parts of song embeddings that are relevant to the aspect we want to focus on (2) a metric learning approach, proposed by Veit et al. [34] and Lee et al. [18], that encodes information about different aspects of a song in separate parts of its embedding. We applied the feature-weighting method to both content-based and CF-based embeddings such as WMF item factors, whereas we only the disentangled metric learning approach for content-based embeddings. The methods were evaluated quantitatively by inspecting tag co-occurrence between query- and retrieved songs, and qualitatively by inspecting retrieval examples and t-SNE visualisations of the song embeddings. It was found that WMF naturally groups together songs with shared semantic tags, and cannot be outperformed by the content-based disentangled metric learning method. However, the content-based method has the advantage of not suffering from the *cold-start problem*. Furthermore, the feature-weighting method was found to improve performance for both content-based tagging embeddings and WMF. However, the performance increase is only marginal for WMF. Finally, we argue that the evaluation method-

ology is not sufficient to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed systems, but a user evaluation is required.

6.2 Future work

Our experiments have shown that proposed methods have potential to improve the functionality of music retrieval and recommendation systems. In future work, we intend to evaluate the popularity bias of the proposed content-based systems, in order to see whether they solve the popularity bias problem of CF-based recommendation systems. We have observed that content-based methods work, but are outperformed by WMF, suggesting that usage data provides information that cannot be extracted from audio. To leverage the advantages of the both content-based and CF-based methods, using both types of information (audio + usage data) as features is a promising avenue. Futhermore, we aim to improve the quality of the disentangled embeddings ¹ by training on a larger dataset and also including tempo information, and investigate how this influences the performance of the retrieval systems. Finally, the usefulness of the system could be improved by taking into account a greater number of semantic tags ², especially for the 'instrumentation' category.

¹we were unable to match the performance reported by Lee et al. [18]

²in this work, we only used the top-50 most popular tags.

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Appendix A

Retrieval examples for tagging embeddings

In this section we show the retrieval results (see section 4.6.1) for the tagging embeddings produced by the pre-trained "short-chunk CNN" architecture. These examples were left out of the main text for conciseness.

Tag: 'House' (genre)

Table 20: Tagging embeddings results for tag 'House' (genre)

Song	Tags
Armand Van Helden & A-TRAK Present Duck Sauce - aNYway	'soul', 'acoustic', 'funk', 'House'
RUN-DMC - Soul To Rock And Roll	'80s'
Hieroglyphics - The Last One	'Hip-Hop'
Gorillaz - Feel Good Inc (Album Version)	'alternative'
Duran Duran - Girls On Film	'80s'
Trafik - Dirty Word	'electronic'
23 Skidoo - Crossfire	'jazz'
Miike Snow - A Horse Is Not A Home	'electronic'
Eminem - FACK	'Hip-Hop'
Rammstein - Bestrafe Mich	'metal'
Atmosphere - Trying To Find A Balance	'Hip-Hop'

Table 21: Feature-weighted tagging embeddings results for tag 'House' (genre)

Song	Tags
Armand Van Helden & A-TRAK Present Duck Sauce - aNYway	'soul', 'acoustic', 'funk', 'House'
Daft Punk - High Life	'electronic', 'dance', 'House'
Rammstein - Rammstein	'metal'
Madina Lake - One Last Kiss (LP Version)	'pop'
Theory Of A Deadman - End Of The Summer	'rock', 'alternative rock'
Basshunter - DotA (Radio Edit)	'dance'
Mariah Carey - Through The Rain	'pop', 'rnb'
Irene Cara - Flashdance... What A Feeling	'pop', '80s'
Phoenix - One Time Too Many	'indie', 'indie pop'
Emilia - Big Big World	'pop', 'female vocalists'
Michael Gray - The Weekend	'dance', 'House'

Tag: 'female vocalists' (instrumentation)

Table 22: Tagging embeddings results for tag 'female vocalists' (instrumentation)

Song	Tags
Stevie Nicks & Don Henley - Leather And Lace	'rock', 'female vocalists', 'classic rock', '80s'
Feist - Tout doucement	'indie', 'female vocalists'
John Michael Montgomery - Sold	'country'
Anthony Hamilton - Can't Let Go	'soul', 'rnb'
Frou Frou - Holding Out For A Hero	'indie', 'electronic', 'female vocalists'
Blue Foundation - Eyes On Fire	'chillout'
Brad Paisley - Mud On The Tires	'country'
Florence + The Machine - Bird Song Intro	'rock', 'instrumental'
John Michael Montgomery - I Swear	'country'
Steve Lukather - Jammin' With Jesus	'rock', 'instrumental', 'Progressive rock'
Air - Alpha Beta Gaga	'electronic', 'chillout'

Table 23: Feature-weighted tagging embeddings results for tag 'female vocalists' (instrumentation)

Song	Tags
Stevie Nicks & Don Henley - Leather And Lace	'rock', 'female vocalists', 'classic rock', '80s'
Apocalyptica ft. Corey Taylor - I'm Not Jesus	'metal'
Atlantic Starr - Always	'soul', '80s', 'rnb'
Liz Phair - Soap Star Joe	'rock', 'female vocalists'
Jewel - Who Will Save Your Soul	'pop', 'female vocalists', 'folk', '90s'
Midnight Oil - Beds Are Burning	'rock', '80s'
Miley Cyrus - Full Circle	'pop'
Radiohead - There, There	'alternative', 'indie', 'electronic', 'alternative rock'
Delerium feat. Sarah McLachlan - Silence	'electronic', 'chillout', 'ambient'
Pantera - Mouth For War (LP Version)	'metal', 'heavy metal'
Prodigy - Breathe	'electronic'

Tag: '60s' (era)

Table 24: Tagging embeddings results for tag '60s' (era)

Song	Tags
Bob Dylan - Like A Rolling Stone	'rock', 'classic rock', 'folk', '60s'
The Whitest Boy Alive - Gravity	'indie', 'chillout'
Maroon 5 - Until You're Over Me	'rock', 'pop'
Extremoduro - Sol de invierno	'rock'
No Doubt / Lady Saw - Underneath It All	'pop', 'alternative', 'female vocalists'
Steve Goodman - Men Who Love Women Who Love Men	'pop'
Jason Mraz - Not So Usual (Eagles Ballroom Live Version)	'acoustic'
Mariah Carey feat. Boyz II Men - One Sweet Day	'pop', '90s', 'rnb'
Boys Like Girls ft. Taylor Swift - Two Is Better Than One	'pop', 'alternative rock'
Alabama - I'm In A Hurry (And Don't Know Why)	'country'
Prince - Raspberry Beret	'pop', '80s', 'funk'

Table 25: Feature-weighted tagging embeddings results for tag '60s' (era)

Song	Tags
Bob Dylan - Like A Rolling Stone	'rock', 'classic rock', 'folk', '60s'
Enigma - Gravity Of Love	'ambient'
Hermans Hermits - No Milk Today	'oldies', '60s'
Alice In Chains - Queen Of The Rodeo	'90s'
Hermano - Letters From Madrid	'alternative', '00s'
Bloc Party - Helicopter	'rock', 'alternative', 'indie', 'indie rock'
The Smiths - There Is A Light That Never Goes Out	'alternative', 'indie', '80s'
Pearl Jam - Oceans	'rock'
Arcade Fire - Ocean Of Noise	'rock', 'alternative', 'indie', 'indie rock'
Massive Attack - Girl I Love You	'electronic'
Angelic Upstarts - Two Million Voices	'punk'

Tag: 'chill' (mood)

Table 26: Tagging embeddings results for tag 'chill' (mood)

Song	Tags
Donavon Frankenreiter - Day Dreamer	'rock', 'Mellow', 'folk', 'chill', 'acoustic'
Jay-Z - Heart Of The City (Ain't No Love)	'Hip-Hop'
Third Eye Blind - Deep Inside Of You	'rock', 'alternative', 'alternative rock', '80s', '90s'
Bettie Serveert - D. Feathers	'rock', 'indie', 'female vocalists', 'indie rock', '90s', 'indie pop'
Rock Kills Kid - Back To Life (Album Version)	'indie rock'
Goldfinger - Stalker (Album Version)	'punk'
Goldfrapp - Ooh La La	'electronic', 'dance'
Totta Näslund - Hemma Före Mörkret	'rock'
The Cars - Tonight She Comes (LP Version)	'rock', '80s'
Chris Brown - Gimme Whatcha Got	'soul'
Elbow - The Bones Of You	'rock', 'alternative', 'indie', 'indie rock'

Table 27: Feature-weighted tagging embeddings results for tag 'chill' (mood)

Song	Tags
Donavon Frankenreiter - Day Dreamer	'rock', 'Mellow', 'folk', 'chill', 'acoustic'
Damien Rice - Cold Water	'indie', 'beautiful', 'folk', 'acoustic', 'sad'
Incubus - Make Yourself	'rock', 'alternative', 'alternative rock'
Secondhand Serenade - Awake	'acoustic'
All Saints - Never Ever	'pop', '90s'
Explosions In The Sky - It's Natural To Be Afraid	'instrumental'
Bread - If	'70s'
Keyshia Cole - Work It Out	'female vocalists', 'soul', 'rnb'
The Temper Trap - Fools	'rock', 'indie rock'
The Strokes - I'll Try Anything Once	'rock', 'alternative', 'indie', 'indie rock'
Josh Groban - Hymne A L'Amour (Album Version)	'male vocalists'